

SINGLE CHANNEL MICROVASCULAR DELIVERY FOR SELF-HEALING POLYMER COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Microvascular systems have successfully demonstrated self-healing functionality in neat polymers and fiber-reinforced composites alike. Many of the previously demonstrated systems deliver two-part healing agents through isolated microvascular networks to the site of damage where mixing of disparate resin and hardener components occurs to initiate polymerization. Mixing in two-component systems is hindered by small crack separation damage geometries and high viscosity healing agent components. To date, improvements to mixing have been accomplished by design of complex microvascular architectures or alternating pressurization of the two networks to induce chaotic flow in the damage zone. Complex vasculature presents a challenge for sample fabrication and alternating pressurization requires a computerized delivery regimen that lacks autonomy.

Here, we present a microfluidic device that accomplishes *in-situ* mixing of two-part healing agents through a single microvascular channel. Components are sequestered from one another until reaching the damage site, where mixing occurs on length scales commensurate with microchannel diameters. Single-channel delivery eliminates the need for complex or branched vascular architectures and the modular design of the device is compatible with previously demonstrated vascularization techniques. Our approach is suitable for a wide range of two-part healing chemistries and achieves repeatable, autonomous delivery using static pressures after calibrating for healing agent surface energy, viscosity, and stoichiometry

1 INTRODUCTION

The regeneration of damaged biological tissue is common in biological systems. Vascular networks enable the regrowth of living structures by supplying nutrients and oxygen to cells near the injury. Although synthetic vascular materials have been developed to achieve self-healing polymers, early work focused mainly on rebonding internal cracks and did not demonstrate the ability to regenerate lost mass. Large, open damage volumes are problematic for vascular systems because healing agents can “bleed out” from the damaged region due to forces such as gravity and surface tension. White and

coworkers introduced an experimental method to regenerate large, open damage volumes using a two-stage polymer system [1]. The large damage volume recovery process is illustrated in Figure 1. The two-stage polymer was separated into two stable reagent solutions and isolated into adjacent microvascular networks (compositions Table S1). As damage occurred, the vasculature was ruptured, causing the solutions to mix and initiating two simultaneous chemical reactions (Figure 1a and 1b). One reaction proceeded very rapidly (30 s to a few minutes) and transformed the healing agents from a low viscosity fluid to a soft gel network (Figure 1c). A second reaction progressed on a longer timescale and caused a second transition to transform the gel into a robust, structural polymer (Figure 1d). The rapid gelation of the two-stage polymer healing agent is the distinguishing feature of the system that enables the recovery of large damage volumes. Without formation of the gel, liquids are mobile and more susceptible to external forces that may draw the healing agents away from large, open damage volumes. Healing chemistries that polymerize too slowly lead to a “bleed-out” condition where liquids continually drip from the damage zone rather than filling the defect to restore component function.

White *et al.* reported a 97% increase for maximum damage area recovered in a through-thickness cylindrical defect geometry for a gelling healing chemistry compared to non-gelling controls [1]. Beyond 9.0 mm damage diameter, samples only partially filled due to three failure modes illustrated in Figure 1e. First, wetting of the healing agents on either the top or bottom surface of the sample wicked un-gelled healing agents out of the damage volume by capillary forces(①). Second, gel formation inhibited microvascular delivery and interfered with proper mixing, preventing gelation of the system. Without gelation, the components of the two-stage chemistry bled out from the damage volume(②). Finally, the growing gel mass sometimes deflected downward rather than closing the gap in the center of the damage volume(③). Results were reported for a single test protocol and the influence of experimental design on these failure modes was not tested.

Figure 1. Schematic showing the polymer restoration process for a two-stage healing agent system. a) A damage event caused a large, open wound in microvascular material, b) Two-part chemical healing system was released into the damage volume where mixing occurred. Green segments represent gelator A [PEG-based oligomer], blue dots represent gelator B (aldehyde crosslinker) and the red dots represent the monomer solvent. c) Gelation occurred rapidly via acid-catalyzed reaction of the dissolved gelators. d) Polymerization of the monomer solvent into a structural material. e) Failure modes observed during the fill process: ① surface wetting; ② un-gelled reagent dripping; and ③ deflection of the gel [2].

Two-part reactive systems offer the best combination of stability and functionality for microvascular healing agents investigated to date. Poor mixing has been shown to result in lower healing efficiency [3-5] and it also affects maximum fill size in the restoration of large damage volumes [1]. The challenge of inducing mixing between components is significant, and even self-healing systems displaying high healing efficiencies contain a large amount of unreacted resin after a healing cycle. [5] Although pulsed delivery of healing agents improves mixing to disrupt laminar flow in a crack plane [1,3] precise control of pressurized delivery cycles is not fully autonomous.

In natural systems, a single fluid (blood) performs a variety of functions including mass transport and injury response. Since the system is a single fluid, there is no need for mixing and multiple stages of healing are initiated autonomously through various reactive species in response to environmental triggers. All reactive components are present and compatible until triggered by a damage event. The current work seeks to introduce an emulsified healing agent comprised of a single fluid with multiple reactive species to eliminate the need for modulated active delivery and improve mixedness of microvascular self-healing systems.

2 SINGLE CHANNEL MICROVASCULAR SYSTEM

Emulsions consist of fine droplets of one liquid phase dispersed in another liquid phase that is not soluble or miscible. Emulsions are widely applied in the paints, cosmetics, and food industries where microfluidic devices create dispersions of uniform droplets. [6] Immiscibility can be used to “encapsulate” miscible phases from one another through the microfluidic creation of double or triple emulsions. [7] In addition to oil-in-water emulsions, oil-in-oil emulsions are possible for 2 or more immiscible non-aqueous liquids and these systems have proven useful for the synthesis of polymer nanoparticles with water sensitive precursors. [8]

Here, a microfluidic device is constructed to create an emulsion of reactive components for microvascular delivery to a damage site through a single channel. A low viscosity carrier fluid acts as an encapsulant to separate and stabilize the reactive species of a two-part (resin and hardener) system (Figure 2). The fluid circulates with a static pressure rather than a pulsed delivery to result in a system more autonomous than those previously demonstrated. As damage occurs, the circulating fluid exits the closed microvascular system and enters the damage region where vaporization of the carrier fluid takes place. After the carrier fluid is removed, the resin and hardener coalesce, react, and initiate the healing event.

Figure 2 | Schematic for a microfluidic single-channel two-part self-healing material. A carrier fluid separates resin and hardener reactive components traveling through the microvascular channel. As the fluid enters the damage region, the carrier fluid will volatilize to allow coalescence and polymerization.

3 CONCLUSIONS

Volume of each component is controlled through static pressure on reservoirs of reactive components to ensure a proper stoichiometric ratio of each part is delivered to the damage volume. Mixing of the two part healing chemistry is improved because spacing between reactive components is now related to the diameter of the microchannel (~300 μm) and emulsion droplets. Due to the single component design, much more simplified vascular geometries are possible since multiple, interpenetrating features are not necessary. Additionally, the single channel design enables facile delivery of high viscosity materials because the low viscosity carrier fluid will transport the reactive species rather than relying on flow of the high viscosity components. The reduction in pressure drop due to viscosity will allow microvascular systems to function under much lower pressures than previous efforts.

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